

Tracking Category Normalized Citation Index (CNCI) changes: Benefits of combining standard, collaboration and fractional CNCI for performance evaluation and understanding

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Abstract

Category Normalized Citation Impact (CNCI) allows comparisons between research in different fields and is considered a standard indicator for national and institutional comparisons. Fractional and collaboration CNCI supplement the standard approach by considering the increasingly collaborative nature of scientific research. Here, these three CNCI variants are combined to analyze changes in these indicator values over the period 2009 to 2018 for nearly 200 institutions. Using Web of Science data, Chinese institutions are found to be extremely consistent in improvements across all three CNCI indicators with an almost 1:1 nature, while USA and Canadian institutions tend to show declines in values for all three indicator variants. Specific institutions, such as King Abdullah University of Science and Technology, Saudi Arabia, stand out as being regionally exceptional in their CNCI values. Analysis also demonstrates the increasingly collaborative nature of research, with the mean number of institutional partners for both domestic and international collaboration increasing over time. Chinese institutions' unique improvement may be due to Chinese citation practices. Specific institutional improvements may be due to hiring policies. Further work is required to fully address how greater collaboration, as well as research portfolios, affect CNCI indicator values and, therefore, performance evaluation and understanding.

Introduction

Citations accumulate at different rates in different research fields making direct comparisons of citation counts meaningless. Category Normalized Citation Impact (CNCI) puts citations in context by normalizing citation counts by publication year, document type and subject category. It is considered a standard indicator for national and institutional comparisons (Jappe 2020) and a key measure by many policymakers. However, given the increase in (international) collaborations over the past 40 years (Adams 2013), individual author contributions to any work are becoming harder to define and, subsequently, provide equitable shares of a document's CNCI value for performance evaluation. This is particularly relevant for junior scientists as their individual qualities can be lost, affecting promotion and funding opportunities (e.g., Bikard, Murray & Gans 2015; de Fontenay et al. 2018). Consequently, variations of CNCI: fractional (e.g., Waltman & van Eck, 2015) and collaborative (Potter, Szomszor & Adams 2020, 2022) have been formulated with the aim of considering multiple authors through fractional credit and collaboration type, respectively. Previous results (Potter, Szomszor & Adams 2020, 2022) have shown that fractional and collaborative CNCI values are generally lower than those of standard CNCI and tend to agree well with one another. Here, building upon our previous work (Potter, Szomszor & Adams 2022), these three alternative CNCI indicators (standard (s), collaboration (c), and fractional (f)) are used in concert to analyze and explain institutional and, by extension, regional CNCI changes over a ten-year period. This demonstrates the 'profiles not metrics' approach (Adams et al. 2019a; Szomszor et al. 2021) and offers insights into the practicality of combining approaches and its importance in understanding research portfolios and informing research management decision making.

Methods

Data from the Web of Science was sourced for analysis given the following criteria: documents with the type ‘article’ published in the Web of Science Core Collection between 2009 and 2018 inclusive. Thirty institutions were then chosen from five predefined regions: USA and Canada, Eastern Europe (EEur), Middle East-North Africa-Turkey (MENAT), China, and Asia-Pacific (APAC) to measure regional trends. Institutions were chosen semi-randomly to reflect high, middle and low volume article-producing institutions, but must have (co)authored a minimum of 5000 articles over the 10-year period. The dataset included almost 10.5M articles. Institutions were collated from author address information available within Web of Science.

CNCI for each article was calculated in the standard manner: citations counts were normalized by document type, year of publication, and Web of Science subject category. Collab CNCI, defined by Potter, Szomszor & Adams (2020), was calculated in the same manner as standard CNCI but with the additional normalization by collaboration type. The five possible collaboration types being: domestic single institution, domestic multi-institutional, international bilateral, international trilateral, and international quadrilateral plus. Fractional CNCI was calculated at the author level following Waltman and van Eck (2015). This method assigns credit to each author, institution, country etc. on a publication based upon the total, deduplicated number of each on a document. This credit was then multiplied by the article’s CNCI to calculate the fractional CNCI value. An institution’s mean CNCI was then calculated by summing the article CNCIs on which that institution was recorded in an author address and dividing this by the sum of its total fractional CNCI value. The reader is referred to Waltman and van Eck (2015), as well as Potter, Szomszor & Adams (2020), for more thorough descriptions and methodology of each indicator.

Results

Figure 1 plots absolute difference in s-CNCI and f-CNCI against absolute difference in c-CNCI between the years 2009 and 2018 for the five regions. Overall, institutions tend to have a greater s-CNCI improvement than c-CNCI improvement ($s\text{-CNCI} = 1.158 * c\text{-CNCI}$), with the latter greater than f-CNCI ($f\text{-CNCI} = 0.904 * c\text{-CNCI}$).

Chinese institutions strongly follow the identity ($x=y$) line (gradient of 0.97 and 0.89 for s-CNCI and f-CNCI, respectively, vs c-CNCI) with the vast majority having improvements in all three CNCI variants and consequently plotting in the first quadrant (+x,+y). MENAT institutions also tend to follow the identity line (for f-CNCI vs c-CNCI), though more institutions fall into the second (+x,-y) and third (-x,-y) quadrants showing decreases in at least one variant; USA and Canada institutions mainly plot in these quadrants too. APAC institutions are generally concentrated around the origin. Eastern Europe institutions tend to plot in the first quadrant, but with a far greater s-CNCI increase than c-CNCI.

Institutions of note include Northwestern Polytechnical University (NPU), Xi’an, China, which exhibits significant improvement across all CNCI variants (0.78 for s-CNCI, 0.71 for f-CNCI, and 0.74 for c-CNCI) and Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), Cambridge, USA, which exhibits a decline in all indicators (-0.24 in s-CNCI, -0.49 in f-CNCI, and -0.38 in c-CNCI). Some institutions have a mix of increases and decreases in indicator values, for example, Tulane University, New Orleans, USA, has s-CNCI and c-CNCI improvement of 0.49 and 0.16, respectively, but a decline of -0.17 in f-CNCI. However, one of these changes is usually minor (i.e., < 0.05).

Figure 1. Absolute difference in fractional (f)-CNCI (top) and standard (s)-CNCI (bottom) vs collaboration (c)-CNCI values between the years 2009 and 2018

Direct year comparisons for standard and collaboration CNCI values are shown in Figure 2. Eastern European institutions show notable – some significant – increases in s-CNCI. However, these improvements are largely subdued when using c-CNCI, producing a far narrower spread of CNCI values in the most recent year. A similar trend is seen for APAC institutions; however, the University of Adelaide has notably distanced itself from its peers in 2018. The USA and Canada region shows a highly similar spread of standard and collaboration CNCI values between both years. MIT shows a decrease in both indicators but remains the top ranked institution by indicator value. China, unlike the other highlighted regions, tends to show improvements under both variants. In MENAT, King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST) is an outlier in s-CNCI, but not c-CNCI, in 2009, but notably improves its value for both over the period.

Figure 2. Standard (top) and collaboration (bottom) CNCI value comparisons for the years 2009 and 2018 for institutions from five world regions.

Fractional and collaboration CNCI rely, to differing extents, on the numbers of collaborating institutions on papers. Table 1 compares the average number of institutions at each collaboration level for selected institutions in 2009 and 2018. Almost all institutions increase their average partnerships across all collaboration types. Some increases are incremental (Seoul Natl Univ international trilateral partnerships increased from 5.5 to 5.8), while others increase by one whole institution (e.g., MIT international bilateral from 4.5 to 5.5); for international quadrilateral plus, this can be tens of partners (e.g., Tulane University from 19 to 77).

Table 1. Average number of institutions for each collaboration type for selected institutions. Numbers are inclusive of the institution analyzed.

<i>Institution [year]</i>	<i>Domestic multi institutional</i>	<i>International bilateral</i>	<i>International trilateral</i>	<i>International quadrilateral plus+</i>
NPU [2009]	2.3	3.1	5.0	-
NPU [2018]	2.6	3.5	5.3	7.9
MIT [2009]	4.2	4.5	7.2	50.4
MIT [2018]	4.8	5.5	7.7	58.3
KAUST [2009]	-	3.2	4.3	6.7
KAUST [2018]	2.2	3.0	4.8	9.4
Univ Adelaide [2009]	2.9	3.9	4.9	29.5
Univ Adelaide [2018]	3.6	4.0	5.9	93.0
Seoul Natl Univ [2009]	3.0	3.8	5.5	49.2
Seoul Natl Univ [2018]	3.6	4.5	5.8	85.1
Tulane Univ [2009]	4.4	4.8	6.6	19.2
Tulane Univ [2018]	5.8	5.2	7.1	77.3

Discussion

Results demonstrate that most institutions see an increase in CNCI values. CNCI indicators do not necessarily reflect a “zero-sum game” due to the collaborative nature of research. Domestic papers are generally less cited than internationally collaborative ones (e.g., Narin, Stevens & Whitlow 1991; Potter, Szomszor & Adams 2020, 2022). The pool of papers for any given institution includes both their (generally lower cited) domestic output and more highly cited international output, which will also appear in the output for any partnering institutions. However, when considering global output, each paper (whether a highly cited internationally collaborative article or a rarely cited domestic paper) is only considered once resulting in an opaquely depressed world average that boosts the relative standing of institutions’ CNCI and illustrates another effect of international collaboration on evaluation.

Some institutions do show declines in CNCI values (third quadrant in Figure 1), and these are mainly USA and Canada institutions such as MIT and University of Quebec that were already highly ranked by CNCI in 2009. This demonstrates that it is easier to improve in CNCI standing with a few more highly cited papers if starting at a lower level but very hard if an institution is already established as a top performer. MIT demonstrates this well as its values decreased despite its increased international collaboration (Table 1) which, theoretically, should improve its CNCI standing. An additional effect of collaboration is seen in the suppression, relative to s-CNCI, of c-CNCI for Eastern Europe, MENAT and APAC (Figure 2). This illustrates that s-CNCI for institutions in these regions is likely driven by highly cited, highly multilateral papers

that, when normalized by collaboration type, do not perform as well, decreasing the indicator value (e.g., Potter, Szomsor & Adams 2022).

Chinese institutions appear relatively immune to using different CNCI indicators showing similar improvements in all three and, therefore, plotting in the first quadrant of Figure 1: taking account of collaboration either fractionally or by collaboration type seems to make little difference, in contrast to other world regions (Figure 2). Several factors could explain this phenomenon. First, China's scientific output has grown rapidly over the last 20 years making it the second largest scientific producer globally (behind USA) in the most recent year of this analysis (2018). Secondly, Chinese publication citation characteristics differ from the worldwide citation distribution (Stahlschmidt & Hinze 2018); China researchers tend to cite their fellow citizens more often (Tang, Shapira & Youtie 2015; Bakare & Lewison 2017; Shehata & Al-Rubaish 2019), as well as citing authors from some Asian countries more than others (Tang, Shapira & Youtie 2015). Additionally, Chinese authored research tends to have longer reference lists than the world average (Stahlschmidt & Hinze 2018). Finally, articles authored by Chinese researchers are increasing their presence in the references of other countries' publications, while, for example, USA-authored articles are experiencing a slow decline (Khelifaoui et al. 2020).

Unusual increases in CNCI indicator values may also be due in part to hiring policies, particularly hiring of Highly Cited Researchers. These researchers, selected by the Institute for Scientific Information (ISI) at Clarivate, have demonstrated significant and broad influence reflected in their publication of multiple highly cited papers over the last decade. These highly cited papers rank in the top 1% by citations for a field (or fields) and publication year in the Web of Science. For KAUST and University of Adelaide their number of highly cited researchers increased from 5 in 2014 to 13 and 10, respectively, in 2018 (R. Fry, personal communication, November 7, 2022). Consequently, the hiring and potential citation impact of HCRs could positively influence an institution's CNCI.

Changes and differences in CNCI indicators could also be due to research foci – institutions focused on large, highly multi-lateral projects would likely receive low fractional credit. The increasing trend of highly multi-institutional, multi-lateral papers is seen in Table 1. How these papers perform relative to their peers (i.e., same collaboration type) would influence its collaboration CNCI value. However, further work is needed to fully explore institutional research profiles to gauge the importance of this factor in interpreting CNCI indicators.

Finally, these results illustrate the advantage of combining CNCI indicators to overcome some of their weaknesses, such as s-CNCI not accounting for collaboration and f-CNCI assigning credit fractionally. Fractional and collaboration CNCI also help normalize by number of authors/countries as highly multi-authored papers have different citation patterns, though they account for a relatively small percentage of published papers (e.g., Adams et al. 2019b).

Conclusion

The use of multiple CNCI indicators allows a profile view of an institution to be collated. As well as understanding how these indicators work, it is also important to understand the research portfolio and collaborations of an institution. Ultimately, without full knowledge of both aspects, such indicators cannot be fully understood in context, which may negatively affect research evaluation and funding decisions.

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